

Lichen Bioindication of Pollution based on Tree Colonization

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Summary

Lichens are pollution sensitive and have been used as bioindicators for quality air. Their distribution in cities mirror traffic pollution distribution as well as other urban lichen factors in relation to this pollution including lichen colonization sources and moisture presence. The objective of the study was to determine the relationship among factors of pollution, moisture and sources of colonization in the determination of distribution of lichen in oak trees. The trees were carefully selected from different sites to reduce correlation in moisture, pollution, and sources of colonization. The study utilized model-averaged standardized regression coefficients in comparing the relative effects of the variables of the cover and richness of lichen. The study found that the lichen cover was correlated to pollution intensity. On the other hand, the richness of macrolichen cover was found to be strongly related to moisture and sources of colonization than to pollution. The findings of the study also suggested that it is advisable to increase the sources of colonization of lichen promote the diversity of macrolichen.

Introduction

Lichens absorb nutrients together with harmful molecules from water and air. Lichens are not able to process or isolate the absorbed harmful molecules faster metabolically to evade damage. For this reason, lichens are sensitive to pollution of the air. A number of studies have suggested that various air pollution forms have impacts on lichens as well. The distribution of

lichens in urban areas is correlated to the urban air pollution patterns, and as a result, lichens have been used to map urban air pollution. Mapping pollution by studying lichen distribution patterns was designed in the industrial pollution context including the effects of industrial agriculture on semi-natural and natural areas. In modern cities, motor vehicles and other automobiles produce air pollution bulk.

Vehicle pollution remains one of the most significant factors affecting the growth of lichen. This does not necessarily implying that the distribution of lichen is dictated primarily by pollution by vehicles. There are a range of variables apart from air pollution that affect the growth of lichens in natural habitats. These include the microclimate and moisture content of the local site within a city setting which affects the cover and richness of lichens.

At the same time, a big percentage of greenhouse gas emission comes from agricultural production, changing the weather patterns and making farming an unreliable occupation. Fertile land, reliable weather patterns, which are the basic requirements for food production, are growing scarcer by the day. Lichens are made of fungus and algae or cyanobacteria which work together. They neither have roots or protective surfaces nor cannot filter what they absorb and thus take in anything that is in the air. Pollutants alike accumulate in lichen and become toxic fast. Out of this, they make good air pollution indicators as they are very sensitive and respond to pollution in short periods of time. Frogs, butterflies, toads and nematodes can also be utilized for the same purpose but not as fast and as easier as lichens in responding to environmental change. Pollution affects lichen distribution in an area. It is difficult to untangle the effects of colonization, pollution and moisture on the distribution of lichens due to the fact that patterns of local moisture and sources of lichen colonization vary with pollution patterns across an area of

city. Pollution levels vary with impervious surface areas since some areas experience more pollution than others.

Methodology

Lichen cover and lichen species richness on five species of oak trees were sampled. The oak trees were taken from roadside sites, one in each grid 1 square kilometer placed over the sample area. From these, a subset of sample sites that minimized correlations on vehicle pollution, sources of colonization, local moisture and impervious surface area. The predictor variables were measured that represented the effect hypothesized. Vehicle pollution was then estimated by adding the road density and bus traffic ranged values together. Road density and bus traffic were measured at a number of spatial extents around every site of sampling lichens. Vehicle traffic was averaged at annual daily vehicle traffic multiplied by a corresponding length of the route in every landscape, ranged between one and zero.

It was assumed that lichens colonize trees from nearby trees and establish on tree branches in the surrounding area of the site centers. Sources of colonization influence were estimated by using the area on square meters of all the oak tree crowns in the area surrounding each lichen sample site. The sources of colonization were standardized using natural logarithm of the oak tree area, and calculated at multiple spatial extents around every site.

For each of the 5 trees, coverage and diversity at both eye-level and at ankle-level were recorded, in each of the four cardinal directions, with accompanying photos. The data is on a 0-10 scale; in terms of coverage, 0 meant none at all, while 10 meant completely covered; in terms of diversity, 0 would mean 1 species of lichen, 1 would mean 2, and so forth until 10, which would be 10 species or more.

Sources of colonization and vehicle pollution were calculated within landscapes at multiple spatial extents in each sample site. Lichens are affected by mechanisms that operate at different spatial scales. The spatial extent upon which pollution and sources of colonization influence cover by lichen and species of lichen, a priori, was not unknown. Due to this, the variables were estimated at ten spatial extents between 100meters and one kilometer. The 10 meter lower limit was designed to capture the vegetative dispersals within small scales while the one kilometer was chosen as sufficient to capture air pollution variation. The scale of the each predictor effect variable was estimated using spatial extent within highest Pearson correlation coefficient. Predictor variable was measured at its effect scale for further statistical modeling.

For lichen survey, five Oak tree species were selected at the sampling site. The selection was based on local availability and similar lichen flora. Macrolichen cover and species richness were sampled on each tree. The survey was limited to macrolichens, the species growing in leafy and bushy forms and is loosely attached to the bark of the trees as opposed to growth within the bark. Macrolichens are apt indicators of lichen diversity growing on trees. They can be identified in the field and are commonly used in public monitoring protocols. Identifying lichens growing within the bark of trees can be time consuming and require also of laboratory identification. For this reason, it is not feasible for extensive surveys. This study uses the word 'lichens' to refer to macrolichens, and otherwise will be stated. A lichen ladder was placed on four sides of each oak trees at 90 degrees apart. The first side was placed parallel to and faced the road. The identification of lichens were the done in twenty regularly spaced one centimeter diameter circles for each micoquadrat. Lichen species and the bare bark with the highest cover per circle were then recoded. Reference specimens were then collected. Richness of lichen species referred to

the number of lichen species recoded in each tree. The cover of lichen referred to the number of circles with presence of lichens.

The study used linear mixed effects modeling in the estimation of the relative effects of pollution, sources of colonization and moisture on lichen cover and the richness of species. The data was analyzed at the tree levels to make it easy to account for the diameter of the trees and the species of the trees as random effects. The species of the trees correlated with the number of microscale variables including pH and texture of the bark. There were seven possible models for the three standardized predictor variables of pollution, sources of colonization and moisture. The models incorporated the diameter and species of the oak trees. Akaike Information Criterion was used in the comparison of the support of models. Tree diameter conclusion was underpinned by decrease of at least eight points in the Akaike Information Criterion values with the inclusion of the tree diameter in any of the models. The relative effects of the predictor variables were compared using weighted model-averaged standardized parameter estimates.

Findings

Eighteen lichen species were found, and which covered an average of 27% of the total of the surface area of the sampled trunk. The most commonly found species included the *Candelaria concolor*, *Physciella chloantha* and *Xanthomendoza fallax*. Moisture was found to vary considerably among 5-day periods, underpinning the se of residual values from the means of each week. The two oak tree species, *Quercus stellata* and *Quercus alba*, had the highest lichen cover and richness of species the other three species varied considerably in terms of cover and richness in species. The effect scales for the predictors, pollution and sources of colonization were found to have the spatial extents and largest absolute correlation coefficients with each

lichen response. Therefore, there is one scale effect identified for each variable-response pairs. The effect scale for pollution was 300 meters and 1000 meters for richness and lichen cover. The correlation coefficients between predictor variables were very low, with -0.37 between pollution and moisture, 0.34 between sources of colonization and moisture, and -0.19 between sources of colonization and pollution.

The coefficient signs across models were found to be consistent with the anticipations as the influence of pollution was negative and the sources of colonization and moisture influences were found to be positive. The best lichen cover models included pollution as a variable. Lichen species richness models also had similar supports. Model-averaged standardized parameter estimate comparison for each variable indicate that pollution is the strongest lichen cover predictor as sources of colonization and moisture remained predictors of lichen species richness stronger than pollution (Sett and Kundu, 2016).

Discussion

The results of the study show that lichen can be used as indicators for traffic pollution and lichen diversity conservation. The lichen cover in the sampled area indicated pollution within 30 meters as the richness in lichen species was not affected by pollution at the 100m to 1000m scales. This implies that lichen cover can be used in the estimation of spatial distribution of pollution in a city. Lichen cover conservation efforts should therefore be focused on increasing trees areas all over a city to provide sources of dispersal instead of controlling traffic pollution since richness in urban lichen species more strongly respond to treed areas as compared to pollution.

References

Sett, R., & Kundu, M. (2016). Epiphytic lichens: their usefulness as bio-indicators of air pollution. *Dannish Journal of Research in Environmental Studies*, 3(3), 017-024.